

ISic4384

Painted funerary naiskos

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

aedicula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Found in recent excavations in tomb 4bis of isola 73 (via C. Battisti, Messina)

Coordinates

38.181815, 15.548299

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Soprintendenza stores

Physical Description

A limestone funerary aedicola, with a painted slab in the recessed central panel. A painted inscription (currently unpublished) is preserved along the upper cornice.

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Painted

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation lines 1 to 2: mm

Text

1.

Apparatus

Not yet published

Translation (en)**Translation (it)****Commentary****Digital identifiers:****Bibliography**

Burgio, R. 2017. Frammenti di architettura lapidea dall necropoli meridionale.

In Tigano, G.(eds.), *Da Zancle a Messina 2016. Nuovi dati di archeologia urbana*.
Palermo. pp. 85-104. At 86 fig.4 and 103 n.10

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